

EVALUATION OF ACID CONCENTRATION ON OBTAINING NANOCRYSTALS CELLULOSE AND SURFACE MODIFICATION BY SILANE

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Abstract – In this study, the influence of H₂SO₄ concentration on the particle size distribution of cellulose nanocrystals (NCC) was evaluated, as well as, the surface modification of nanoparticles by silanization. Eucalyptus cellulose sheets kindly provided by CENIBRA were hydrolyzed with 20, 30 e 50 % (v/v) H₂SO₄ solutions for 40 minutes at 40 °C. The samples were named CV20, CV30 and CV50, respectively. Samples were centrifuged at 6,000 rpm at 10°C for 30 minutes until pH 6-7. Subsequently, it was lyophilized and characterized according to the size distribution by laser dispersion (DLS), zeta potencial (PZ), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), field emission scanning electronic microscopy (FEG), transmission electronic (TEM) and infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). Samples were lyophilized and redispersed (1% w/v) in 100 mL of anhydrous ethanol by sonication at 30% amplitude for 30 minutes. Another solution was prepared with anhydrous ethanol and 5 mL of (3-Aminopropyl) triethoxysilane (APTES) under stirring for 30 minutes and acidified with acetic acid to pH 4 – 5. The solutions were stirred for two hours. After this time, the solution was centrifuged and washed with ethanol and centrifuged again (three cycles) to completely remove the residues. The DLS analyses showed that increasing the H₂SO₄ percentual influenced the particle size distribution. Only the CV50 sample showed hydrodynamic diameter of 256 nm and PZ equal to -26.0 mV. FEG and TEM microscopies confirmed the obtaining of nanocrystals when 50% (v/v) H₂SO₄ was used. TGA analyzes indicate that the reaction with APTES increased the thermal stability of the NCCs. However, FTIR spectra not evidenced the surface chemical modification of nanocrystals cellulose.

References

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